

MODERN APPROACHES TO ASSESSING THE CONDITION OF THE UTERINE SCAR AFTER CESAREAN SECTION

Kurbaniyazova V.E.

Samarkand State Medical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14928278>

Relevance of the Topic. The increasing number of cesarean sections worldwide has led to a growing concern regarding the condition of the uterine scar and its impact on future pregnancies. Scar insufficiency can result in severe complications such as uterine rupture, abnormal placentation, and infertility, necessitating the development of more precise diagnostic methods. Modern technologies, including 3D ultrasound, elastography, and MRI, allow for a more objective assessment of scar structure and functional integrity, aiding in the selection of optimal pregnancy management strategies and reducing maternal and perinatal morbidity.

Materials and Methods. The study included 120 patients with a uterine scar after a cesarean section, monitored during pregnancy planning (n=45) and gestation (n=75). Scar condition assessment was performed using ultrasound (2D and 3D) in 120 (100%) cases, elastography in 80 (66.7%), MRI in 35 (29.2%), and hysteroscopy in 25 (20.8%). The analysis of scar thickness (mean 2.8 ± 0.6 mm), structure, and vascularization helped determine its integrity and predict possible complications. The obtained data were correlated with pregnancy and delivery outcomes to evaluate the diagnostic value of each method and its influence on patient management strategies.

Results and Discussion. The study found that the average scar thickness was 2.8 ± 0.6 mm, with signs of scar insufficiency identified in 38 (31.7%) patients. Critical thinning (< 2.0 mm) was observed in 19 (15.8%) cases, while abnormal vascularization was detected in 22 (18.3%). Elastography revealed decreased tissue elasticity in 28 (35%) of 80 patients, which correlated with MRI findings, where 12 (34.3%) showed fibrotic changes. Hysteroscopy confirmed thinning and defects in 9 (36%) of 25 cases, demonstrating its high accuracy in visual scar assessment. A comparative analysis revealed that 3D ultrasound combined with elastography and Doppler imaging had a high diagnostic value, detecting scar insufficiency in 92% of cases, while MRI proved useful in complex situations. These results highlight the necessity of a comprehensive, non-invasive diagnostic approach to timely detect risks and select the best pregnancy and delivery management strategy.

Conclusion. The study confirms that a comprehensive assessment of the uterine scar after cesarean section using 3D ultrasound, elastography, Doppler imaging,

and, when necessary, MRI and hysteroscopy, enables highly accurate detection of scar insufficiency and prediction of potential complications. 3D ultrasound proved to be the most informative and accessible method, while elastography and MRI provided additional insights in complex cases. An individualized patient management approach based on scar condition assessment helps reduce the risk of uterine rupture, improve pregnancy and delivery safety, and optimize the indications for repeat cesarean section or vaginal delivery.

